

THE EFFECTS OF INTERNAL STRESS ON THE THERMAL PROPERTIES OF T300/LD2 COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

In order to analyse the reason of producing hysteretic loop and residual strain in thermal cycling, we have designed several composite materials which possessed different internal stresses by cooling and heating pre-treatment. The experimental results proved that the primary reason causing the hysteretic loop and the residual strain were large amount of elastic and plastic deformations which occurred alternatively and unequally in matrix in thermal cycling. The methods of minimizing the residual strain and hysteretic loop have been proposed.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites are composed of reinforce fiber and alloy matrix with different properties. Their characteristic of thermal response are different with those of metal materials. Li [1] and Crossman [2] had studied the properties of thermal expansion of carbon fiber reinforced aluminum composites. The results showed that the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of the composite in different temperature range are different. When the composite were cycled from room temperature to 673K, the expansive and contractive process of these materials were unreversible. Wolf [3] got the same results. The reasons for the residual strain and the hysteretic loops are not clear and there are a few studies about the methods to improve these properties. It is an unfavorable factor for some parts demanded by high dimensional stability that possessing large and unstable residual strain in the service condition with varied temperature. In order to analyse the reason of producing hysteretic loop and residual strain in thermal cycling, this paper have designed several composite materials which possessed different internal stresses by cooling and heating pre-treatment. It has been studied how internal stresses affect the CTE, hysteretic loop & residual strain of the composite in thermal cycling. The methods of minimizing the residual strain and hysteretic loop have been proposed.

EXPERIMENT

The specimen was the T300/LD2 composite which was made by hot pressing of the T300/LD2 precursor and aluminum foils in vacuum. The dimension of the specimen is $\Phi 3 \times 10$. The specimens were treated in vacuum or under the protection of Ar gas. The treatment parameters are shown as Table 1.

Table 1. Heating Treatment Processing

No.	cooling and heating treatment processing
T1	673K for 1Hr, cooling in furnace
T2	793K for 20 Min, water quenching, 423K for 8 Hrs, cooling in furnace
T3	T2 + quenching in liquid nitrogen
T4	T1 + quenching in liquid nitrogen
T5	793K for 20 Min. quenching in liquid nitrogen

The CTE of the specimens treated by different cooling-heating treatments had been measured at the temperature range 293K-673K. The CTE at the different temperature ranges had also been measured in thermal cycling.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The CTE of the T300/LD2 specimens after different treatments are listed at Table 2. It is found that the CTE of the specimens after the T3, T4, T5 treatment are all very low in the temperature range 293-473K at first thermal cycle. At the second thermal cycle, the CTE of specimens after T3, T4, T5 treatment increased greatly. The curve of thermal deformation versus temperature of specimens treated by T2 & T3 processing (see Fig. 2, Fig. 3) showed that there were two stages in the elevating temperature courses, elastic stage (A-B see Fig. 2, Fig. 3) and plastic stage (B-C see Fig. 2, Fig. 3). Comparing with the T1 & T2 treatments, the quenching in liquid nitrogen contracted largely the elastic stage of the first thermal cycle, but affected slightly the elastic & plastic stages of the second thermal cycle. The effect of cooling treatment is different according to the matrix microstructure states before the cooling treatment. For instance, before the liquid nitrogen treatment in T3 treatment, the matrix was in the state of quenching and followed by artificial aging. It possessed higher yield strength. In T4 treatment, the matrix is in anneal state before the liquid nitrogen treatment, so it had lower yield strength.

Table 2. The CTE of The T300/LD2 Composite After Different Treatments

CTE	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
$\alpha_1 \times 10^{-6}$	5.44	6.61	2.55	1.32	2.84
$\alpha_2 \times 10^{-6}$	5.04	7.89	6.97	4.70	6.99

Note: α_1 means the even CTE at the 293-473K temperature range in elevating temperature of the T300/LD2 at the first thermal cycling from 293K to 673K.

α_2 means the even CTE at the 293-473K temperature range in elevating temperature of the T300/LD2 at the second thermal cycling from 293K to 673K.

If not considering the physical and chemical change in matrix, fiber and interface, the unidirectional continuous fiber reinforced MMCs can be expressed as a mechanics unit as shown in Fig.1. It can be ideally considered that the stress in the fiber and matrix are respectively even, the interface bonding between fiber and matrix is good and the load is conveyed from one place to another through the shear mechanism of the interface. Supposing the materials are in the state of plane stress, the fiber and matrix are under ideal longitudinal tensile stress and transverse shear stress, we get the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= V_f \sigma_1^f + V_m \sigma_1^m \\ \sigma_2 &= \sigma_2^f = \sigma_2^m \\ \tau_{12} &= \tau_{12}^f = \tau_{12}^m \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_1 &= \epsilon_1^f = \epsilon_1^m \\ \epsilon_2 &= V_f \epsilon_2^f + V_m \epsilon_2^m \\ \gamma_{12} &= V_f \gamma_{12}^f + V_m \gamma_{12}^m \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here the subscript f and m denote the fiber and matrix respectively. Subscript 1 and 2 mean two directions parallel or perpendicular to the aligned fibers. The unidirectional continuous fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composite satisfied with the above supposition.

Figure 1. The Micromechanics Unit for Unidirectional Continuous Fiber Reinforced MMCs

Supposing the internal original stress between fiber & matrix of T300/LD2 specimens before elevating temperature is σ_T^{mo} . When the temperature is increased from T_0 to T_1 , the additional stress will be produced in the matrix because of the large difference of the CTE between T300 fiber and LD2 matrix. The stress change in thermal cycle is classified two stage: (1) $|\sigma_1^m| < |\sigma_1^{0.2}|$, the elastic stage. (2) $|\sigma_1^m| > |\sigma_1^{0.2}|$, the plastic stage. In the elastic stage, the strain of fiber and matrix can be expressed by:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_1^m &= \alpha_m(T_1 - T_0) + \sigma_1^m / E_m \\ \epsilon_1^f &= \alpha_f(T_1 - T_0) + \sigma_1^f / E_f \\ \epsilon_1^f &= \epsilon_1^m \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

It can be obtained that the relationship between the matrix stress and temperature when the matrix is in the lastic deformation stage.

$$\sigma_1^m = \sigma_T^{mo} + (T_1 - T_0) \cdot V_f \cdot E_f \cdot E_m (\alpha_f - \alpha_m) / (V_m E_m + V_f \cdot E_f) \quad (4)$$

When $\sigma_1^m = \sigma_1^{0.2}$ (at elevating temperature range, $\sigma_1^{0.2}$ denotes matrix compressive yield strength; at decreasing temperature range, $\sigma_1^{0.2}$ denotes matrix tensile strength), this temperature is defined as T_T . When $T > T_T$, the matrix produced plastic deformation. The T_T can be drawn from the equation (4) as following:

$$T_T = T_0 + (\sigma_1^{0.2} - \sigma_T^{mo}) (V_m E_m + V_f \cdot E_f) / V_f \cdot E_f \cdot E_m (\alpha_f - \alpha_m) \quad (5)$$

For the T300/LD2 composite specimens, when $\sigma_T^{mo} = -\sigma_1^{0.2}$, it can be obtained that $T_T = T_0 + 150$ from equation (5). So the matrix always produced elastic and plastic deformation in the elevated temperature process from room temperature to 473K. When the matrix is in the elastic deformation stage, the CTE of the composite can be expressed as the equations (6):

$$\alpha_e = (\alpha_m V_m E_m + \alpha_f V_f \cdot E_f) / (V_m E_m + V_f \cdot E_f) \quad (6)$$

For the T300/LD2 composite specimen from the equation (6), it can be got that α_e is $7.06 \times 10E-6/K$. The experimental α_e is $6.64 \times 10E-6/K$ which is consistant with the calculated result. Basically, the α_e don't change with the variety of the temperature. When the matrix is in plastic deformation, the CTE of the specimen was determined by that of fiber [6]. So the even CTE of the T300/LD2

specimen from room temperature to 473K can be expressed as the following:

$$\alpha_1 = [\alpha_e \cdot (T_T - T_0) + \alpha_p \cdot (473 - T_T)] / (473 - T_0) \quad (7)$$

The specimens which were treated by different cooling or heating treatments possessed different original internal stresses in matrix. The internal stresses of specimens treated by T1, T2 processing are pulling force. The internal stresses of specimen conducted by T3, T4, T5 processing are pressing force [4]. From equation (4), with elevating temperature, the additional stress which was produced by the large difference of the CTE of fiber and matrix was compressive stress.

Fig.2 T300/LD2, T2 treatment, thermal cycling from room temperature to 673 K

Fig.3. T300/LD2, T2+quenching in liquid nitrogen treatment

It can be found from the equation (4) that the existing of the pre-fabricated residual compressive stress, σ_T^{mo} , greatly decreased the value of T_T . Substituting the equation (5) into (7), it was found that the α_1 also greatly decreased. The calculated results are completely consistent with the fact that the CTE of specimen treated by the liquid nitrogen treatment decreased largely, which showed in Table 2.

The fact that the value of T_T largely decreased after the liquid nitrogen treatment is also consistent with the experimental results. The figures 2-3 show the curves of thermal deformation-temperature of the T300/LD2 composite specimen treated by T2 & T3 treatment. It is found from the figures that the temperature range of the elastic deformation stage (A-B) of the matrix is largely shortened after the liquid nitrogen treatment and that of the plastic deformation (B-C) of the matrix become longer.

In the decreasing temperature period of the thermal cycling, the matrix of the T300/LD2 specimens is also conducted in the elastic and plastic deformation stage, which is consistent with experimental results as shown in the figures 2-3. From the figures 2-3, the residual strain of the T300/LD2 by the liquid nitrogen treatment after first thermal cycle from 293K- 673K is larger than that of T300/LD2 by anneal treatment. It can be found that the residual strain of the specimens treated by the anneal treatment after first cycle from 293K-673K is $5\mu\text{m}$. But for these specimens treated by the liquid nitrogen treatment, the residual strain reach to $10\mu\text{m}$. In the second thermal cycle, the internal original stresses of specimens treated by different cooling and heating processing equal to the yield strength of the matrix, so the effects of pre-fabricated internal stress disappeared. From Tab 2, Fig. 2, 3, the same conclusion can be obtained. The curve of thermal deformation versus temperature of T300/LD2 cycled from room temperature to 353K were showed in Fig. 4. From Fig. 4, it is found that the process of the expansion and contraction were reversible, there were no residual strain.

Fig.4 T300/LD2, T2 treatment, thermal cycling from room temperature to 353 K

The above analysis showed that the liquid nitrogen treatment mainly decreased the T_T temperature, and decreased or increased the temperature ranges when the matrix is in the elastic or plastic deformation. So the large amount of the plastic deformation increased the unreversible behavior of the expansion and contraction for the T300/LD2 specimens in thermal cycling from 293- 673K. It is the elastic and plastic deformations alternatively and unequally occurred in the thermal cycling that results in the appearance of the hysteric loops and residual strains.

Three methods to decrease the residual strain & hysteretic loop have been proposed. First, minimizing the temperature change of the service condition of composite. Second, making the matrix of composites in elastic deformation in the working condition by different pre-treatment. Third, increasing the yield strength of the matrix.

CONCLUSION

The T300/LD2 composite materials possess low CTE. It is the elastic and plastic deformations occurred alternatively and unequally in thermal cycling that results in the appearance of the hysteretic loops and residual strains.

Three methods could be used to decrease matrix plastic deformation and the residual strain. First, decreasing the temperature variety in the service condition as large as possible. Second, making the matrix of composite in the state of elastic deformation by means of different pre-treatment according to the service condition of the materials. Third, increasing the yield strength of the matrix.

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